

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT REINFORCEMENTS ON THE CREEP BEHAVIOUR OF ALUMINIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Three aluminium matrix composites, Al-20 vol.% SiC_p, Al-20 vol.% TiB_{2p} and Al-20 vol.% TiC_p produced by powder metallurgy technique, were creep tested under compression in the temperature range 573-723 K. The steady state creep data of these composites showed very high values of apparent stress exponents and activation energies similar to the dispersion strengthened materials. These data were rationalized in terms of the constant substructure model, which predicts a stress exponent of 8, subgrain size exponent of 3 and an activation energy equal to the lattice self-diffusion in aluminium, together with the existence of a threshold stress. A comparison of the creep strength of these composites suggests that SiC particulate is the most suitable reinforcement for high temperature applications.

INTRODUCTION

During recent years, there has been burgeoning interest in the development of discontinuously reinforced aluminium (DRA) matrix composites for high temperature applications. This has led to a number of studies on the creep behaviour of DRA composites [1-11]. Most of the studies are, however, related to the steady state creep behaviour of SiC reinforced aluminium matrix composites. The reinforcements based on TiB₂ and TiC also appear to be important for aluminium matrix due to the following reasons: (a) TiB₂ has very high modulus which can give rise to better composite strengthening and (b) TiC has good wettability with aluminium [12] that can lead to improved interface between matrix and particles which in turn can provide better creep resistance of the composite.

The objective of the present paper is two fold: (a) to study the effect of different reinforcements on the steady state creep mechanisms of aluminum matrix composites, and (b) to evaluate the extent of creep strengthening derived from these reinforcements.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three aluminium matrix composites, Al-20 vol.% SiC_p (1.7 μm), Al-20 vol.% TiB_{2p} (4 μm), and Al-20 vol.% TiC_p (1.4 μm), made by powder metallurgy (P/M) route were used. The P/M route used for Al-SiC and Al-TiB₂ consists of blending of aluminium powder with reinforcing particles, cold isostatic pressing, sintering followed by section rolling. For Al-TiC composite, vacuum hot pressing and extrusion were used after degassing the cold compact. Both the routes resulted in the composite rods, which were used for microstructural examination and creep testing. Compression creep tests were conducted using a creep machine with constant load facility. Specimens with gauge length of 10 mm and gauge diameter of 5 mm were used. The creep strain was measured using two linear variable displacement transducers (LVDTs) mounted on the ridges provided with the compression grip. The temperature of the specimens was maintained within 2K. In order to reduce friction of the specimen with the compression plates, molybdenum disulphide was applied at ends of the specimens.

RESULTS

Scanning electron micrographs (Figs. 1a to 1c) of Al-SiC, Al-TiB₂ and Al-TiC composites show uniform distribution of reinforced particles in the Al matrix. The agglomeration of TiC particles (Fig. 1c) could be due to the improper blending of Al and TiC powders during processing.

A comparison of tensile and compression creep curves for an Al-10 vol.% SiC composite [4] is shown in Fig. 2. This indicates that the minimum creep rate of tension does not correspond with the steady state creep rate of compression. The tertiary creep starts in tension even before the beginning of steady state during compression. This is related to the early

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrographs of (a) Al-SiC, (b) Al-TiB₂ and (c) Al-TiC composites.

Figure 2. A comparison of tensile and compression creep curves for Al-10 vol.% SiC composite.

onset of cavitation at the SiC particles during tensile creep of composite [4]. It appears that the compression creep data can be used for meaningful evaluation of steady state creep mechanisms in composites.

In the present work, creep rate-stress plot for Al-SiC composite shows very high values of apparent stress exponents 18.5, 23.2, and 29.9 at 623, 673 and 723 K respectively (Fig. 3a). There is no significant variation in stress exponent with the applied stress. This is possibly because of the limited creep rate range (10^{-9} to 10^{-6} s⁻¹) of the data available. The apparent stress exponents for Al-TiB₂ composite also show very high values and increases from 16 to 20.8 with the test temperatures (Fig. 3b). Also, a variation in apparent stress exponent with applied stress is noted for Al-TiB₂ composite. For example, the apparent stress exponent is 22.5 in low stress range (less than 27 MPa) which decreases to 13.5 in the high stress range (greater than 27 MPa). The creep rate-stress plot for the Al-TiC composite also exhibits high value of apparent stress exponent, 16.6 like other composites but no appreciable variation with applied stress is observed (Fig. 3c). The apparent stress exponents for the composites observed in the present study are similar to those reported for other aluminium alloys (6061 Al and 2124 Al) composites [1-2,5,8].

The apparent activation energy for creep of Al-SiC composite is found to be 249 kJ mol⁻¹ at a constant stress of 40 MPa (Fig. 4a). This value is similar to the activation energy for creep of Al-TiB₂ composite (Fig. 4b). Although the apparent activation energies for creep of Al-SiC and Al-TiB₂ composites vary with the applied stress, we report the value of an activation energy at a reasonably high stress to avoid the influence of threshold stress. The values of apparent activation energies observed for the present composites are higher than theoretically expected activation energy for self-diffusion in aluminium, 142 kJ mol⁻¹ [13].

DISCUSSION

1. Evaluation of Steady State Creep Mechanism

The present data can be analyzed using constant substructure model of Sherby et al. [14] given by

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \left(\frac{D_1}{b^2} \right) \left(\frac{\lambda}{b} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_0}{E} \right)^8 \quad (1)$$

where D_1 is the lattice self-diffusion coefficient, λ is the subgrain size, b is the magnitude of Burgers vector, E is the Young's modulus and σ_0 is the threshold stress below which no appreciable deformation takes place. Eq. (1) predicts a stress exponent of 8, subgrain size exponent of 3 and an activation energy close to the lattice self-diffusion. The data for these composites are plotted in terms of $\dot{\epsilon}^{1/8}$ against applied stress on linear scales in Figs. 5 a to 5c. The linearity of the data indicates that power law creep relation with a stress exponent of

Figure 3. Variation of steady state creep rate with applied stress for (a) Al-SiC, (b) Al-TiB₂ and (c) Al-TiC composites.

8 is appropriate for these composites. Further, these plots are used to determine the threshold stress for composites by extrapolating the linear regression lines to zero creep rate. The values of threshold stress are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of threshold stress for Al-SiC, Al-TiB₂, and Al-TiC composites

Material	Stress exponent, n	Temperature, T (K)	Threshold stress, σ_0 (MPa)
Al-20 vol.% SiC composite	8	623	25.2
		673	25.1
		723	25.8
Al-20 vol.% TiB ₂ composite	8	573	16.1
		623	14.3
		673	14.4
Al-20 vol.% TiC composite	8	623	17.1

The true activation energy for Al-SiC composite is found to be 205 kJ mol^{-1} at a constant normalized stress, $(\sigma - \sigma_0)/E = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (Fig. 4a). Similarly, the true activation energy for the Al-TiB₂ composite is 187 kJ mol^{-1} at $(\sigma - \sigma_0)/E = 2 \times 10^{-4}$. The true activation energies for these composites are still slightly higher than the expected value of activation energy, 142 kJ mol^{-1} [13]. This could be due to the scatter in the data of composites. However, if the data of composites are plotted in terms of lattice diffusivity compensated creep rate, $\dot{\epsilon}/D_1$ vs. modulus compensated effective stress, $(\sigma - \sigma_0)/E$ as shown in Figs. 6a and 6b, then all the data merge together on a single line with a slope of 8. This makes strong suggestion that the creep data of these composites can be rationalized using constant substructure model of Sherby et al. [14]. This is consistent with a comprehensive study on aluminium alloy composites reported by Gonzalez-Doncel and Sherby [8].

2. Threshold Stress

Table 1 shows that the values of threshold stress for Al-SiC composite are higher than those for Al-TiB₂ and Al-TiC composites. The threshold stress does not show an appreciable dependence on test temperatures. Mohamed et al. [5] have suggested attractive interaction between dislocation and oxide particle as the origin for the threshold stress for 6061 Al-SiC composite. However, the dependence of threshold stress on the volume fraction of SiC particles [6] can not be explained by the dislocation-oxide particle interaction mechanism. The load transfer to the reinforced particles appears to be the likely origin for the threshold stress in composites [6]. The efficiency of load transfer depends on the modulus of the reinforcements. Since the modulus of TiB₂ is higher (551 GPa) than those for SiC (480 GPa) [15] and TiC (451 GPa), threshold stress for the Al-TiB₂ composite should be higher than both the composites. However, the observed values show the opposite trend. Also, despite the similarity in the modulus for SiC and TiC, the Al-SiC composite shows higher value of threshold stress than that of Al-TiC

Figure 4. Variation of $(\text{creep rate})^{1/8}$ with stress for (a) Al-SiC, (b) Al-TiB₂ and (c) Al-TiC composites.

Figure 5. Arrhenius plots in terms of creep rate vs. $10^3/T$ for (a) Al-SiC and (b) Al-TiB₂ composites.

Figure 6. Variation of $\dot{\epsilon}/D_1$ with $(\sigma - \sigma_0)/E$ for (a) Al-SiC and (b) Al-TiB₂ composites showing that all the data merge together on a single line.

composite. This could be possibly related to the nature of interface between matrix and reinforced particles. A perfect interface is likely to provide maximum load transfer to the reinforcement.

3. Creep Strength

A comparison between the steady state creep strength of composites, plotted as an equivalent creep rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}$ [7] vs. applied stress (Fig. 7) indicates that while the creep strength of Al-TiC composite is better than Al-TiB₂ composite, it is inferior to Al-SiC composite. The creep strength of the composite depends on the subgrain size (interparticle spacing) and the threshold

Figure 7. A comparison of creep strength of Al-SiC, Al-TiB₂ and Al-TiC Composites showing highest strength for Al-SiC composite.

stress. The higher creep strength of the Al-SiC composite as compared to the Al-TiC composite appears to be related to the threshold stress because the interparticle spacing for both the composites are almost similar. The lower creep strength of the Al-TiB₂ composite than the other composites could be due to the larger interparticle spacing and the lower threshold stress.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A comparison of tensile and compression creep curves of an Al-SiC_p composite suggests that a proper steady state regime exists only in compression.
2. The steady state creep rate vs. applied stress data for Al-SiC_p, Al-TiB_{2p} and Al-TiC_p composites showed very high values of apparent stress exponent and activation energy.
3. The steady state creep data for these composites can be rationalized in terms of a stress exponent of 8 and an activation energy close to the lattice self-diffusion in aluminium predicted by constant substructure model [14], together with a threshold stress.
4. The threshold stress as well as the steady state creep strength for the Al-SiC_p composite are higher than those for Al-TiC_p and Al-TiB_{2p} composites. SiC appears to be the most suitable reinforcement for the aluminium matrix for high temperature applications.

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